

FILM – INDUCED TOURISM: THE IMPACT OF DESTINATION EXPOSURE OF LOCALLY-MADE JAPANESE MOVIES ON TRAVEL INTENTION TO JAPAN

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Abstract: Japan has long been a prominent film destination, having given the world Akira Kurosawa (1910-1998), the great film director and cult movie figure. The influence of Japan on Hollywood production is evident and well – established however there are limited studies concerning the influence of locally made Japanese movies in film – induced tourism in Japan. There exists an underutilized opportunity of destination exposure in Japanese film markets through locally made movies that can induce audiences’ travel behavior; thus, it is crucial to understand the impact of destination exposure specific in the Japanese film market. The study adapted the modified meaning transfer model, and this characterizes product placement as a transformative process whenever viewers can see the things without needing to utilize them. Experimental Quantitative research design was utilized in this research with 30 respondents chosen through purposive sampling. This established the following factors to effectively and objectively gather data: (1) treatment factors which is destination exposure, (2) the scope or variation of attributes in which the treatment factors were measured are affective attribute and affective affinity, (3) the manner in which the data were gathered and recorded through pre – testing and post – testing of a Likert scale modified instrument which measure travel intention through familiarity of culture and attractions and the desire to visit Japan, (4) the criteria provided the conclusions and implications for the recorded data as well as the treatment of paired T-test. The study found that destination image as a single determinant is significant factor in influencing travel intention of the participants. Age showed significant difference with travel intention before exposure to destination image while desired duration of travel is found to be significant in familiarity of destination image before exposure.

Keywords: destination image, destination exposure, travel intention, modified meaning transfer model.

1. INTRODUCTION

Film tourism, the phenomenon of individuals traveling to destinations or landmarks because of their connection to a film or television series, has exploded in popularity over the last decade. This is arguably not a new phenomenon, since the film and television industries have affected people's movement and tourism almost since the invention of cinema, thanks to its integrated system of celebrity and fanbase (Kim and Reijnders, 2017). As elaborated by Strielkowski (2017), despite the rising popularity of film-based tourist promotion, little attempts have been made to uncover the fundamental factors that underpin the concept of film - induced tourism. Moreover, the value of film-induced tourism for location marketing has been highlighted by academics and practitioners because of its established effect as a tool in inducing travel decisions or

intentions through determinants such as destination exposure. Even though there is a link between authenticity and destination loyalty or the intention to travel, some of the studies have investigated the different possible mechanisms through which authenticity impacts destination loyalty (Teng and Chen, 2021). Therefore, the aim of the study is to understand the impact of destination exposure specifically to the locally made Japanese movies on travel intention to the study.

As elaborated by Mahardika (2021), images can influence how people see certain destinations thus it is considered as one of the decision-making tools in the tourism industry that builds motivation for people to travel. In studies involving marketing tourism, destination exposure is the audiences' collection of thoughts, feelings, and beliefs wherein travel decisions could be determined (Mege & Aruan, 2018). However, there exists an underutilized opportunity of destination exposure in Japanese film markets through locally made movies that can induce audiences' travel behavior, thus it is crucial to understand the impact of destination exposure specific in the Japanese film market (Strielkowski, 2017). On the other hand, the term travel intention is mainly described as the audiences' behavioral response to determinants; in this case, it is categorized as the destination exposure. As a matter of fact, individuals' travel intentions strongly influence their touristic behavior in the present and the future (Yıldırım, Yalçınkaya, Çöker, Küçük, and Görman, 2017). In addition, the study is deeply anchored in exhibiting experimental treatments through various exposure of locally made Japanese movies to the audiences.

Japan has long been a prominent film destination, having given the world Akira Kurosawa (1910-1998), the great film director and cult movie figure. Kurosawa's triumph with "Rashomon," which won the Golden Lion at the Venice Film Festival in 1951, opened Western film markets to Japanese films and helped to the blending of the two film cultures. Moreover, the popularity of films either related to or taking place in Japan is enormous in the Western world (Strielkowski et al. 2017). Although the storylines are set in Japan or are at least related to Japanese culture, most of the films that boosted Japanese tourism are produced by Hollywood media and are not locally made. Currently, most of the research on film-induced tourism is focused on Western – made films only situated in Japanese destinations. Thus, it is within the aim of the study to rationalize the impact of locally made Japanese movies on film – induced tourism through destination exposure to further understand the current state of film- induced tourism in locally made Japanese movies.

The influence of Japan on Hollywood production is evident and well – established however there are limited studies concerning the influence of locally made Japanese movies in film – induced tourism in Japan (Yeo, 2021). As the Japanese government has been actively involved in establishing country branding initiatives to further enhance Japan's exports and tourism. The popularity and richness of Japanese culture makes marketing of Japanese destinations more conceivable thus the use of locally made Japanese movies can be a viable way to induce travel intentions. (Mahardika et al, 2021). It is the aim of the study to emphasize the current state of Film – induced tourism on locally made Japanese movies to understand how it differs from Hollywood movies with Japanese locations.

The study formulated a single general question which exemplifies the impact of destination exposure in locally made Japanese movies on travel intentions to Japan. This is centered on the specific and relevance of the problem concerning the study. In other words, the general question of the study is preceded by specific questions of such nature:

- Impact of Film – Induced tourism in Japan;
- The pattern of effectivity of the stimuli from the experiment;
- Behavioral change from the comparison of pretesting and post testing of the treatment;

Although, exposure to destination image (destination exposure) is one of the established concepts wherein travel decisions could be measured (Mege and Aruan, 2018), limited studies are present when it comes to destination exposure being utilized as a single determinant as well as demographic profile in mediums such as locally made Japanese movies. Hence, the study hypothesized that:

- There is a significant difference between destination image and respondents travel intention to Japan
- There is a significant difference between destination image and respondent's demographic profile

The researchers formulated the research objectives which are to determine how destination exposure of locally made Japanese movies acts as a single determinant in inducing travel intentions to the respondents, to obtain a descriptive comparison and understanding of the capability of locally made Japanese movies to Hollywood based Japanese movies, and to measure changes of travel intentions before and after the destination exposure from the locally made Japanese movies.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND CONCEPTUAL/THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A destination's appearance in a film is the pinnacle of product placement (Mege & Aruan, 2018). The modified meaning transfer model was chosen for this study as it investigates the influence of movie genre on destination image, familiarity, and travel intention. The study adapted the modified meaning transfer model to investigate the influence of destination exposure of locally made Japanese movies on travel intention to Japan. Mege & Aruan (2018) characterizes product placement as a transformative process, and the modified meaning transfer model is principally utilized to explain how it works. The transformation is considered a success when viewers can see the things without needing to utilize them. Because of the show's personal relevance, empathy, knowledge, and execution, people are transformed.

With the strong relevance of the new media era, the concept of movies has continued to evolve. As an emerging style of media, movies continue to portray and emphasize local destinations and in turn have sparked a tourism boom (Ding, 2019). With the continuous development in technology, streaming movies are becoming more popular and convenient, thus tourism promotion through movies Film – Induced tourism becomes more relevant (Mege & Aruan, 2018). Furthermore, the present state of the media industry and the tourism industry integration under the trend of media convergence and the growth of movies in the media industry, it is imperative to analyze the rationale behind the audience travel motivation (Ding, 2019). The link between tourists' intentions and their perceived picture of a location has been studied in various ways. Some studies such as (Endah, Umar, Suharyono, & Andriani 2017), and (Kanwel, Lingqiang, Asif, Hwang, Hussain, & Jameel, 2019) found a link between perceived image and travel visit intent. Travel decision-making prefers places with a favorable image claim that it is required in positive decision-making for the destination to have a positive image. The positive impression of a location must outweigh the negative (Al-Adamat, 2020).

Marketing process tools are useful in both personal and public marketing activities, as they target not only physical but also psychological, emotive, and sensational experiences of individuals (Yıldırım et al.,

media, word of mouth, and posters together with destination exposure to understand its impact on travel intention. In this study, destination exposure is used as a single determinant to know its impact on travel intention rather than with other determinants.

There is always a positive association between customer value perceptions and readiness to buy. As a result, potential travelers' travel plans are studied to gain insight into the important issues (Chiu, Ting, Alamanzeh, & Hua, 2019). Yıldırım et al., (2017) elaborated that individuals' behavioral response to determinants are travel intentions that strongly influences their touristic behavior in the present and the future. With this, travel intentions measures travel behavior that can have a possibility to travel, fueled by the commitment to travel, and stimulated by motivation to travel. Thus, it can be inferred that the possibility, commitment, and motivation to travel are three factors that influence travel behavior.

If the destination is adequately exposed to the respondents, there is a link between destination image and intention to visit. The product indicates that after seeing the film, participants' perceptions of the place improved, and they were more likely to visit the location (Mege & Aruan, 2018). The influence of new media on the elements that influence young people's

travel destinations cannot be overstated (Ding, 2018). To better build the concept of film induced tourism in Asia, studies must focus on the contents rather than the media (Nakayama, 2021). With these in mind, generally, it is critical to understand the principle behind Film-induced Tourism through its contents, such as destination image as a single determinant, rather than the media. According to numerous studies, having travel information equates to a better destination image and greater travel intention.

Scenarios of film induce tourism can also be found in Asia. For instance, locally produced Chinese Film “If you are the one,” with scenes that exposes several Japanese locations stimulated tourist to visit locations presented in the movie specifically in Easter Hokkaido in 2008 (Seaton and Yamamura 2015). Table 1 shows blockbuster films that sparked tourism rush in various Japanese locations.

The capacity to influence and attract international cooperation by persuasive means such as culture rather than outright cash or coercion, is shown by Japan's exports of television, movies, and toys. They've even risen to prominence as a source of national pride. Japan's worldwide image has shifted dramatically in just a few decades, particularly in the West. The changes have been so dramatic that it might be difficult to identify the same nation in these many perspectives. But, as rapid as Japan's transformation into a pop-cultural behemoth seemed, it took time and the perfect combination of circumstances—economic, and integration of western production (Bain, 2020). Between 2010 and 2015, the number of Western visitors visiting Japan increased by 50%. Many of these visitors are drawn to Japan by films that are linked with the country in some manner. Although it is established that Chinese tourists account for most inbound visitors to Japan, the marketing potential of film-induced tourism in Japan remains unexplored. Several recent Western films set in Japan have contributed to the rise in appeal of Japan as a tourist destination (Strielkowski, 2017).

Figure 1: Number of tourists visiting Japan (2009- 2015)

Figure 1 shows the overall number of tourists that visited Japan between 2009 and 2015, showing the proportion of visitors from Asia, Europe, North America, and Australia. The number of visitors visiting Japan has doubled in the previous six years while this blockbuster films were produced (from 6 million in 2009 to almost 13 million in 2014). This age group aligns the aim of the study with the background literature.

3. METHODOLOGY

Experimental Quantitative research design was utilized in this research. This established the following factors to effectively and objectively gather data: (1) treatment factors which is destination exposure, (2) the scope or variation of attributes in which the treatment factors were measured are affective attribute and affective affinity, (3) the manner in which the data were gathered and recorded through pre – testing and post – testing of a Likert scale modified instrument which measure travel intention through familiarity of culture and attractions and the desire to visit Japan, (4) the criteria provided the conclusions and implications for the recorded data as well as the treatment of paired T-test. The experimental design of the study centered on determining whether destination exposure as a treatment influences travel intentions of the respondents. It is important to realize that the study adapted a within – subject experimental design. It is important to realize that the study used three (3) movies at a sample size of 30, thus each movie has ten (10) respondents, and the duration of participation is expected within this manner is at most a day.

The independent variable in this study is the destination image which determines the travel intentions of the respondents through its exposure by locally made Japanese movies. Consequently, it is presumed that a change in the methodology of exposure of the destination image resulted in a significant change to the travel intention, thus the dependent variable of the study is travel intention. Controlled variables that were included in the study are the streaming platform use for the movies, the language use in both voice and captions, the online synchronous environment, and resolution of the movie. Moreover, the researchers used young adults as the participants which is the primary phase from adolescence to adulthood (usually defined as the period from approximately 18 to 34-year-olds) (Vespa, 2017). Furthermore, young adults tend to be actively organizing future travel plans and intentions (Nguyen et al., 2021), thus the study used respondents within. In this study, the researchers measured the influence of destination exposure to travel intentions of the respondents. The group was exposed to destination images within the locally made Japanese movies chosen for the study. These movies are the following: "We made a beautiful bouquet," "Liar x Liar," and "Aristocrat." These three movies were chosen because they presented numerous shooting destinations where the respondents can be more exposed which in turn may provide high touristic value.

In addition to this, the researchers adapted and modified a five-point Likert scale and demographic instrument from the study "Determinants of Travel Intention among Foreign Students in Malaysia - Perspective from Push-Pull Motivations" (Chin, Leng, Yuan, & Xiong, 2015). The demographic instrument is specific for studies that deal with travel intentions, it includes age, gender, desired frequency of travel, desired duration of travel, and preferred style to travel. On the other hand, the five-point Likert scale includes questions of possibility, commitment, and motivation to travel within the context of destination image. Furthermore, these measures were both administered to pre-test and post-test to provide significant values that are needed to infer significant conclusions and results after statistical treatment. Hence, the researchers used paired t-test for the comparison of pre-test and post-test values. It must be remembered that this statistical treatment was used for all the pre-test and post-test values of the movies with different respondents. Different statistical results, although identical in procedure, are completely independent and isolated from each other; it was compared descriptively after inferences are done.

The researchers gathered thirty (30) respondents using purposive sampling with emphasis on respondents ages 18 – 34 years old with the capacity and desire to travel internationally, respondents should at least have college level educational attainment. Purposive sampling was used in this study. The main standard for the respondent's profile is age, as literature suggests that young adults between the age range discussed above are the ones that are more active in their travel behaviors. Moreover, characteristics of the respondents were given importance to strengthen the data sample. These characteristics include has history traveling domestically or internationally, has travel plans, and affinity to movies.

Moreover, the thirty (30) respondents were divided equally into three (3) identical and isolated groups in which the only difference is the movie that they were exposed to. Each group has ten (10) respondents that passed the purposive sampling of characteristics that were treated equally as far as the controlled variables and standards are concerned. Furthermore, groups are then pre-tested by the five-point Likert scale that measures travel intentions and changes in destination image perception. After the groups were pre-tested, independent treatment of destination exposure for each group was implemented. This included exposure to locally made Japanese movies that contain local destinations and tourist attractions. Treatment was implemented using Google Meet as a streaming platform for the respondents. As soon as the treatment is finished, post-testing was implemented to the respondents. In this way, they still have a complete recall of the movie thus a more vibrant destination image is present. After all the necessary data had been generated, the researchers used different statistical analysis including the measure of central tendency, paired t-test and standard deviation to know if change in value of the data is significant enough in concluding that the destination exposure as a single determinant through locally made Japanese movies have significant influence on travel intentions of respondents to Japan. Lastly, the data that had been statistically treated were used to arrive at certain conclusions regarding the influences and implication of destination exposure of locally made Japanese movies to the travel intentions of the respondents.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter presents the findings, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered on travel intention of millennials through movie viewing. This also shows the results of the statistical tools for obtaining the demographic profile of each participant, their response to the treatment, and their travel intention after the treatment. The descriptive statistics results, comparison, and the interpretation are organized according to the research questions addressed.

The percentage and frequency distribution of the participants by age are shown in Table 1. Of the 30 participants, 21, or 70%, were 22-25 years old which shows the dominating age in the study. This information might suggest that most of the participants are millennials in collegiate level.

Table 1. Age of the Respondents

Age Bracket	Frequency	Percentage
18-21 y/o	5	16.67
22-25 y/o	21	70
26-30 y/o	3	10
31-34 y/o	1	3.33
Total	30	100%

The study's demographics are consistent with the current millennial domination in the tourism market. Given that there are more millennials than any other generation, with a population of over 80 million, millennials are seen as a lucrative and desirable market, piquing the attention of many businesses (Weber, 2017; Acheron, Mundo, Restar, & Villanueva, 2018). Moreover, millennials see travel as a vital component of their lives, are especially drawn to the consumption of experiences in traveling (Sofronov, 2018), thus tourism studies that investigate travel intention normally have millennials as their participants.

The percentage and frequency distribution of the participants by sex are shown in Table 2. Of the 30 participants, 23, or 76.67%, were female which shows the dominating sex in the study. This information might suggest that most of the participants who are interested in planning travel are females.

Table 2. Sex of the Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Female	23	76.67
Male	7	23.33
Total	30	100%

The findings of the 2008 WTO research on youth travel are supported by this, which emphasizes the growing role of female travelers in the youth market. The percentage and frequency distribution of the participants by desired frequency of traveling are shown in Table 3. Of the 30 participants, 10, or 33%, were inclined to travel once a year. The data in this demographic varies but the highest preferred frequency of traveling is once per year. This information might suggest that most of the participants are inclined to travel occasionally.

Table 3. Desired Frequency of Traveling

Desired Frequency	Frequency	Percentage
Once a year	10	33.33
Twice a year	6	20
Three times a year	8	26.67
More than three times a year	6	20
Total	30	100%

Table 4. Desired Duration of Traveling

Desired	Frequency	Percentage
Duration		
1 – 3 days	5	16.67
4 – 6 days	18	60
More than 7 days	7	23.33
Total	30	100%

According to Chui (2023), the healing effects of a vacation; a reasonable length was more healing than a length that was too lengthy or too short. The research revealed that individuals who traveled for a moderate amount of time (longer or shorter) participated in demanding (relaxing) activities at least once. This confirms the data in the study that moderate duration can be more beneficial.

The percentage and frequency distribution of the participants by preferred style of traveling are shown in Table 5. Of the 30 participants, 23, or 76.67%, were inclined to travel casually. This preferred style

In the study of Ana & Istudor (2019) millennials travel frequency yields a total of 55.7% which they take to travel no more than five times each year, 36.7% make five to ten travels, and 7.6% make more than ten travels per year. This implies that millennials tend to travel less per year which the data in this study yield the highest.

The percentage and frequency distribution of the participants by desired duration of traveling are shown in Table 4. Of the 30 participants, 18, or 60%, were inclined to travel for 4 to 6 days. This desired duration indicated the highest. This may indicate that participants may want to travel longer but not week long. indicated the highest. This may indicate that participants prefer to travel casually as it will enable them to travel spontaneously and according to their liking.

Table 5. Preferred Style of Traveling

Traveling Style	Frequency Percentage	Preferred
Casual	23	76.67
Formal	1	3.33
Pre - organize	6	20.00
Total	30	100%

In a survey of millennial travelers, it was found that 49% of them booked last-minute casual trips due to their spontaneity and constant search for recreational activities (Ramgadge & Kumar, 2021). This data confirms this demographic of the study in which millennials are inclined to travel casually where they can do whatever they want during the travel duration.

The respondents' full scores on the statements pertaining to their familiarity with the destination image in Japan in both pre-test and post-test is included in Table 6. The indications presented below are primarily based on these claims. Based on each mean, all the statements in pre-test acquired agreeable interpretation with three statements having strongly agree and two statements having agree. The statement,

"Beautiful landscapes in Japan will turn on my vacation mood," earned the highest mean and accounted for 3.67, showing strongly agreed remarks. Moreover, all the statements in post-test acquired agreeable interpretation with all the statements having strongly agreed. Both in pre-test and post-test the statement, "Beautiful landscapes in Japan will turn on my vacation mood," earned the highest mean. In the study of Sohn & Yoon (2016) which focuses on Japanese tourists, it has been elaborated that exposure of destination images such as landscapes and cities before the actual travel to Japan show significant destination satisfaction of tourists which in turn shows significant increase in destination attachment.

Table 6. Overall Destination Image Statements

	Pre - Mean		Mean	
I expected destinations in Japan to be relaxing.	3.53	Strongly Agree	3.73	Strongly Agree
Safety in Japan is my concern	3.33	Agree	3.67	Strongly Agree
Beautiful landscapes in Japan will turn on my vacation mood.	3.67	Strongly Agree	3.88	Strongly Agree
opportunity to experience Japanese culture.	3.63	Strongly Agree	3.80	Strongly Agree
One vacation allows me to learn the history of tourism in Japan.	3.43	Agree	3.80	Strongly Agree
Total	3.52	Strongly Agree	3.77	Strongly Agree

3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.49 Agree, 1.50-2.49 Disagree, 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree

The respondents' full scores on the statements pertaining to their travel intention in Japan in both pre -test and post – test is included in Table 7. The indications presented below are primarily based on these claims. Based on each mean, all the statements in pre-test acquired agreeable interpretation with all statements having an agreed interpretation. The statement, "The motivation to travel at younger age is higher," earned the highest mean and accounted for 3.49, showing an agreed remark. In post-test, all statements earned strongly agree interpretation. The statement, "The motivation to travel at younger age is higher" also yield the highest mean having 3.80 and earning a strongly agreed remark. In the study of Phú & Bagul (2020) which focuses on destination image situated in Japan's Tohoku district, it has been emphasized that formation of affective image through sensory and cognitive image like movies have the largest effect in travel intention and the likelihood of travel is immense compared to other motivational methods.

Table 7. Overall Travel Intention Statements

	Pre - Mean			
I am willing to travel and tour within Japanese locations presented in the movie.	3.34	Agree	3.67	Strongly Agree
I have perceptions of how travel to	3.33	Agree	3.63	Strongly Agree
I am committed to travel to Japan because I know other people travel experiences	3.23	Agree	3.67	Strongly Agree
There is a high possibility that I would travel to Japan because it aligns with my personal values.	3.23	Agree	3.60	Strongly Agree
The motivation to travel at younger	3.49	Agree	3.80	Strongly Agree
Total	3.237	Agree	3.67	Strongly Agree

3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.49 Agree, 1.50-2.49 Disagree, 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 8 shows if there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test of both destination image and travel intention. The difference in the respondent's assessment of the destination image and travel intention before and after the exposure is found to be significant since the t-values of 2.318 and 3.301 have p-values less than 0.05 significance level. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected. This indicated that there is a change in the assessment of destination image and travel intention of the respondents after the exposure to the movies. With this, based on the overall means after exposure is higher for both destination image and travel intention.

The results revealed that involvement of destination image from electronic sources showed favorable cognitive and affective image of Japan thus a higher desire for possible tourist to plan a trip to Japan. This study confirms the data emphasized in the t – test with difference in the treatment used.

Table 8. Paired Sample T – Test of Pre-test and Post-Test

<i>Measure 1</i>	<i>Measure 2</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
Pre-test destination image	Post-test destination image	-2.318	29	0.028
Pre-test travel intention	Post-test travel intention	-3.301	29	0.003

With t-values not significant at the 0.05 level, Table 9 shows that the participants' familiarity of destination image and travel intention before and after exposure to the movies is unrelated to their sex. It means that their familiarity of destination image in Japan and their travel intention is not dependent on their sex.

This also implies that sex has no influence on millennials in traveling in Japan through the exposure of destination image from movies.

Table 9. Comparison by Sex

	Group	Mean	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Pre-test destination image	Female	3.478	-0.652	0.52	Not significant
	Male	3.657			
Post-test destination image	Female	3.757	-0.504	0.618	Not significant
	Male	3.829			
Pre-test travel intention	Female	3.348	0.321	0.751	Not significant
	Male	3.257			
Post-test travel intention	Female	3.704	0.847	0.404	Not significant
	Male	3.571			

With t-values not significant at the 0.05 level, Table 10 shows that the participants' familiarity of destination image and travel intention before and after exposure to the movies is unrelated to their age, with exception on pre-test travel intention. Pre-test travel intention yields a significant value of 0.011 which is significant. This implicates that the familiarity of the participants in destination image cannot be influenced by age before and after exposure to the movies. In travel intention, only before exposure to the movies have been found that age significantly affects their travel intention. This indicates that without exposure to the movies, age can be a primary influence on millennials. But with proper exposure to the movies age becomes less influential to the participants they tend to be more inclined to be motivated to travel by the movies.

Table 10. Comparison by Age

	18-21 y/o	22-25 y/o	26-30 y/o	f- value	p-value	Interpretation
Pre-test destination image	3.00	3.57	3.9	2.82	0.077	Not significant
Post-test destination image	3.52	3.82	4.00	3.973	0.056	Not significant
Pre-test travel intention	2.60	3.51	3.25	5.32	0.011	Significant
Post-test travel intention	3.36	3.72	3.8	2.575	0.095	Not significant

With t-values not significant at the 0.05 level, Table 11 shows that the participants' familiarity of destination image and travel intention before and after exposure to the movies is unrelated to their desired frequency of travel. It means that their familiarity of destination image in Japan and their travel intention is not dependent on their desired travel frequency.

This also implies that millennials who travel regularly or less does not affect how they perceive destination image as well as their travel intention to travel specifically to Japan.

Table 11. Comparison by Desired Frequency

	Once a year	Twice a year	Three times a year	More than three times a year	f- value	p-value	Interpretation
Pre-test destination image	3.26	3.767	3.6	3.6	0.946	0.433	Not significant
Post-test destination image	3.76	3.767	3.95	3.567	1.699	0.192	Not significant
Pre-test travel intention	3.28	3.533	3.325	3.2	0.278	0.841	Not significant
Post-test travel intention	3.66	3.733	3.825	3.433	1.477	0.244	Not significant

With t-values not significant at the 0.05 level, Table 12 shows that the participants' familiarity of destination image and travel intention before and after exposure to the movies is unrelated to their desired duration of travel. With exception of before exposure to the destination image where it had been found significant.

Duration of 1-3 days have been found to be significant to the familiarity of destination image before exposure where it yields a p value of 0.043. It means that familiarity of destination image may be dependent on duration of travel before any exposure.

Table 12. Comparison by Desired Duration

	18-21 y/o	22-25 y/o	26-30 y/o	f- value	p-value	Interpretation
Pre-test destination image	3.00	3.57	3.9	2.82	0.077	Not significant
Post-test destination image	3.52	3.82	4.00	3.973	0.056	Not significant
Pre-test travel intention	2.60	3.51	3.25	5.32	0.011	Significant
Post-test travel intention	3.36	3.72	3.8	2.575	0.095	Not significant

With t-values not significant at the 0.05 level, Table 13 shows that the participants' familiarity of destination image and travel intention before and after exposure to the movies is unrelated to their preferred style of traveling. It means that their familiarity of destination image in Japan and their travel intention is not dependent on their preferred style of traveling.

This indicates that whatever style of travelling millennials employ in their travel their familiarity of destination image and their travel intention is not directly influenced by this factor.

Table 13. Comparison by Preferred Style of Traveling

	Group	Mean	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Pre-test destination image	Casual	3.504	-0.243	0.81	Not significant
	Pre-organized	3.571			
Post-test destination image	Casual	3.713	-1.913	0.066	Not significant
	Pre-organized	3.971			
Pre-test travel intention	Casual	3.226	-1.59	0.123	Not significant
	Pre-organized	3.657			
Post-test travel intention	Casual	3.609	-1.845	0.076	Not significant
	Pre-organized	3.886			

5. CONCLUSION

The survey determined the participants' sex, age, desired frequency of traveling, desired duration of travel, and preferred style when traveling. The questionnaire consists of 10 questions that are related to various indicators of destination image familiarity and travel intention to Japan. These questions were pre-tested and post-tested after the exposure of movies to the participants. The study comprises mostly females. The participants age mostly lies within the bracket of 22-25 years old where their desired frequency of traveling varies but most of the participants preferred to travel occasionally or once per year. In terms of their preferred duration and preferred style of traveling, both yield a majority answer. In preferred duration, 4 to 6 days was the dominating answer while in preferred style for traveling, casual travel dominated.

Based on all available data from the study it had been found that destination exposure and travel intention have significant differences after the exposure of treatment to the participants. In terms of the relationship between destination image and travel intention to the demographic profile of the participants; sex, desired frequency of travel, and preferred style of traveling yield no significant difference. Whereas age and desired duration have been found to be significant in travel intention before any exposure.

As the analysis found that there is significant difference in destination image and travel intention, the researchers concluded that destination image through exposure of locally made Japanese movies influences their intention to travel to Japan. This also indicates that destination image exposure can act as a single determinant in predicting the travel plans of millennials. This can also mean that affective and cognitive images from the movies provide significant influence in future travel plans of millennials. Moreover, with the wide availability of streaming platforms having found that exposure to destination image does influence travel intention, tourism markets can exploit this avenue to further advance their interests in attracting different tourists. However, this study employed movies that are situated in Japan thus the researchers can only conclude that exposure to affective and cognitive images from the destination image in Japan can act solely on its own to attract millennials to travel to Japan. With travel intention having a significant difference with age before exposure to destination image implies that age can be a key demographic in influencing travel intention without proper exposure to destination image. However, after exposure, age became not significant implying that destination image is a much more powerful motivator as it is an external stimulus given to the participants. Moreover, the desired duration to travel made a significant difference with familiarity of destination image before exposure. This indicates that the participants desired travel duration relies on their current expectations of what Japan looks like. In sex, desired frequency to travel, and preferred style no significant difference were found against travel intention and destination image. This may be because these variables can be preference based and cannot be easily motivated by external factors such as destination image.

Based on the established conclusions from the determined and interpreted data results, the following recommendations are suggested. Sex demographics are mostly dominated by females thus a purposive sampling that employs equal amounts of female and male participants as well as other gender preference to emphasize the use of gender diversity and further examine which gender are likely to be influenced by destination image in motivating them to travel. Moreover, participants should be increased to provide statistical power for further studies. It is also recommended that the streaming of movies should be done physically with the supervision of the researchers. This will eliminate any distractions to the participants. This will also make the environment limited to one making the exposure more reliable since all the participants will be experiencing the same conditions that was pre-made by the researchers. Anime should also be considered if it also influences travel intention with its destination image. Considering that anime is purely animation this will enable future media markets and tourism markets to collaborate if this is a viable option in attracting tourist via their animation. Evaluation of future researchers to other countries as well as domestic travel using destination image is highly recommended as it will examine if exposure to affective and cognitive images is both effective in foreign tourists and domestic tourists. Moreover, with the exposure of destination images from the locally made Japanese movies being significantly effective in influencing travel intention, the researchers recommend the following; The tourism markets in Japan should collaborate with media or streaming companies to make their movies more accessible in other parts of the world. This will make locally made Japanese movies more seen and heard outside of Japan. Thus, the discovery of foreign tourist of the destination in Japan is much easier. Moreover, this will allow foreign tourists to be at ease when researching possible vacation destinations especially if they have seen one in movies. The researchers also recommend to the tourism markets the use of movies, skits, or series that show natural landscapes, community interactions of vacation destinations as this will allow possible tourists to deduct what they will expect if they visit the location. This will allow them to accept or reject the location by comparing them to their values and preferences. Furthermore, evaluation of future researchers to other countries as well as domestic travel should be considered since this will elaborate if destination exposure can be a viable option in influencing travel option on domestic travel.

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